

JACOB, Dionísio. **O hipnótico Berlioz e o misterioso rebuliço em Pirambeiras** [The Hypnotic Berlioz and the Mysterious Commotion in Pirambeiras]. São Paulo: FTD, 2019.

REVIEW¹

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The story takes place in the year 1900 in Pirambeiras, a small town in rural Brazil, during the First Republic. Colonel Cornélio Junqueira is a typical figure of the Brazilian elite that has dominated national politics since then: he makes promises and hands out favours in exchange for votes for his chosen candidate. Whenever such practices fail to produce results, he simply tampers with the vote counts. Until, one day, a mysterious man and self-proclaimed hypnotiser decides to settle in Pirambeiras, causing a real commotion among the locals.

Keywords: History of Brazil. Brazil-Republic. Policy.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2020 Bologna. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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